

International Perspectives of Undergraduate Research

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Abstract

It is important to explore research efforts, opportunities, and accomplishments of various countries. International collaboration allows nations to work together on research and learn from each other, helping to meet societal needs more effectively. This review of the literature offers examples of research priorities in various countries around the world. The databases used to collect this research were PubMed and Google Scholar. Only peer-reviewed articles published within the last five years were included in the search, along with two textbooks, one of which is approximately fifteen years old but was still included for its relevance. The findings of this systematic review revealed differences among research priorities and geographical location.

Keywords: Undergraduate Research, low-income countries, underserved areas, virtual learning.

Introduction

It is crucial to discover what other countries are doing in terms of research methodology. Each country can learn from another, which may improve ways of student learning. Undergraduate research prompts students to continue researching in their careers, improving their lives, and community living. Collaboration and networking across the globe assist both researchers in the learning process.

The research questions for this review are “What are the perspectives of undergraduate research at different institutions across the globe, and what does undergraduate research look like in different countries?”

Methods

This systematic review studied the relationship between undergraduate research perspectives in the United States and in underserved countries. The databases used to collect this research were PubMed and Google Scholar. The inclusion criteria consisted of peer-reviewed articles published within the last five years with full text availability. Literature was chosen based on relevance and time frame.

Results

Fourteen peer-reviewed articles were chosen for this systematic review, as well as two textbooks, one of which is approximately fifteen years old but was still included for its relevance.

Discussion

Benefits of Undergraduate Research

Undergraduate research (UGR) or high-impact practices (HIPs) enhance student education by providing opportunities for critical thinking and problem-solving (Assar et al., 2022; Leonetti et al., 2023; Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022; Rush & Landgraf, 2023; Serbeh et al., 2024). Undergraduate research offers pathways for transformational learning by enhancing awareness of reality and facilitating the prediction of phenomena (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025; Serbeh et al., 2024). UGR enables students to develop skills relevant to the job market and cultivate diverse perspectives, thereby enhancing the likelihood of addressing social and environmental problems in the future (Rush & Landgraf, 2023; Serbeh et al., 2024). When students participate in research, they gain a sense of academic empowerment that allows them to be emancipated from myths to solve social dilemmas (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025; Serbeh et al., 2024). Research addresses social challenges in low-income countries (Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022). Experiential learning or field research enhances understanding of real-world problems and

improves decision-making skills, thereby aiding in the development of culturally liberated or self-reliant societies (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025; Serbeh et al., 2024).

In one study, Arabic universities surveyed undergraduate students participating in research. Students voiced that research is helpful in the profession, and students display positive attitudes toward research, claiming it has increased relevance to their studies (Assar et al., 2022). Students whose parents hold degrees tend to exhibit more positive attitudes towards research, experience reduced anxiety, and participate more actively in workshops. An interesting outcome, female students had higher perceptions of relevance, and males had higher anxiety when undertaking a research project (Assar et al., 2022). In a similar Indian study, females had stronger initiative to complete research when compared to males (Monisha et al., 2024). Perhaps this is leading to an increased number of women becoming institutional presidents and senior institutional officers (SIOs). Women lead with a democratic, collaborative style (Deardorff et al., 2022).

Challenges of Undergraduate Research

There is little emphasis placed on research in underserved areas, as it is considered a low priority due to diminished funding and a lack of qualified supervision (Assar et al., 2022; Mahomed et al., 2022; Rush & Landgraf, 2023). Challenges students face when researching are a lack of experience, limited supervision, anxiety, timeliness, motivation, poor understanding of

expectations, disconnect from reality, funding, language barriers, writing skills, access to materials, software, and fear of failure (Amarante et al., 2021; Assar et al., 2022; Deardorff et al., 2022; Leonetti et al., 2023; Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022; Mehta et al., 2020; Moxley, 2022; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025; Serbeh et al., 2024). Student complaints about research included overemphasis, which led to missing lectures to complete research projects (Serbeh et al., 2024).

Challenges for faculty mentors include allocating time to supervise research projects in addition to other responsibilities (Leonetti et al., 2023; Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). For example, in numerous African institutions, one faculty member may supervise dozens of student research projects, which exceeds the recommended ratios; this results in inadequate mentorship guidance (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Suggestions to improve this dilemma include adopting a group model that promotes collaboration and teamwork, which also reduces the number of projects that faculty supervise. Another suggestion is to provide workshops and professional development to mentors (Erickson et al., 2022; Leonetti et al., 2023; Mahomed et al., 2021; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025; Serbeh et al., 2024; Unnikrishnan et al., 2022). A university in central Africa caps student enrollment to limit the student-to-mentor ratio. This university strongly believes in providing proper guidance, fostering high engagement, and cultivating problem-solvers (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Faculty who are not stressed contribute to the university's academic standing and are more engaged (Monisha et al., 2024).

Researchers from developing countries are underrepresented compared to those from Northern countries (Amarante et al., 2021). Few articles are published in underserved areas; the majority are from the North. Africa allocates a mere 1% of its funding for research (Deardorff et al., 2021); as a result, it produces only 1% of research studies globally (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Africa must invest in research to gain strong partners in global trade (Sangwa Mutabazi, 2025). Surprisingly, articles about underserved areas are published by those who do not live in underserved areas, such as Northern authors (Amarante et al., 2021). Citizens from underserved areas often lack research skills due to a lack of research knowledge (Amarante et al., 2021; Mehta et al., 2020).

Global Research Production

Research productivity varies across Africa, with South Africa being the main publishing area (Moxley, 2022). African authors are more likely to be rejected by journals compared to their North American counterparts, with reasons including plagiarism, poor quality, and unclear contributions (Amarante et al., 2021). The United States and the United Kingdom produce the greatest number of published authors (Amarante et al., 2021). Conferences provide an opportunity for networking, which influences the global research agenda; unfortunately, there are limited conferences held in Africa, which does not help this situation (Amarante et al., 2021).

Impacts on Health Care

Evidence-based practice (EBP) involves the integration of research and expertise to deliver the highest quality patient care. This practice relies heavily on research activities, problem-solving skills, and lifelong learning (Mahomed et al., 2021; Moxley, 2022; Unnikrishnan et al., 2022). Research identifies knowledge gaps, develops diagnoses, treatments, and preventive measures for diseases (Unnikrishnan et al., 2022). There is currently a lack of interest among medical experts in participating in research (Monisha et al., 2024). EBP's impact is crucial for underserved areas, as it benefits society (Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022; Monisha et al., 2024). If UGR is incorporated early into the curriculum, graduates will be prepared to continue researching in their future professions and mentor students themselves, perpetuating the cycle (Monisha et al., 2024). A phenomenon known as the "Brain drain" occurs when students graduate and relocate to improve their livelihood and opportunities, rather than remaining in their current area and utilizing their skills to benefit the community (Abdi & Kapoor, 2009; Deardorff et al., 2022; Mohammad et al., 2021).

Educational Structure in Underserved Areas: Africa and India

Views on undergraduate research vary significantly among institutions worldwide. For instance, undergraduate research at one South African institution is currently an elective process but is predicted to become mandatory in future years (Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022). In another South African institution, research is mandatory, including ethical review, data analysis,

and poster presentation (Mahomed et al., 2021). In West Africa, all undergraduate students are required to participate in research; however, they often demonstrate little engagement or rigor. Research is viewed as a hurdle rather than a transformational experience at this institution (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). In another West African institution, all students are required to participate in research to graduate (Serbeh et al., 2024). However, the discussion of making it elective has sparked some benefits. If elective, faculty may be spared from mentoring uninterested students (Serbeh et al., 2024). UGR in a Southern Indian institution is also an elective process but will become mandated in the future (Unnikrishnan et al., 2022).

Educational Structure in the United States

There are over 1,000 community colleges in the United States, which are typically not research institutions. These colleges attract a diverse student body and are advancing in research as an HIP. These colleges have discovered that UGR increases collaboration, communication, and pro-science attitudes (Leonetti et al., 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted in-person research and led to the shift of virtual laboratories using virtual reality (Erickson et al., 2022). Students commented that their mentors frequently checked in with them, were flexible, and attentive. The strengths of virtual research were quality of mentorship, learning opportunities, and connection to students across the globe (Erickson et al., 2022). Perhaps virtual learning and reality will continue to become more popular and sought after.

Improvement Models

To address accessibility issues in undergraduate research, it is vital for underserved areas to gain public access to databases and software, commonly referred to as open educational resources (OER). This initiative aims to create inclusive learning environments (Rush & Landgraf, 2023; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Undergraduate research offices (UROs) fund research projects, allowing students to participate in presentations with incentives such as exposure, awards, experience, collaboration, funding, and future job placement opportunities (Marais & Gey van Pittius, 2022; Monisha et al., 2025; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025).

It is essential for research to be relevant to students' interests and cultural backgrounds. This describes the cognitive interest or critical study theory, which posits that interest sparks learning (Deardorff et al., 2022; Serbeh et al., 2024). To engage students, experiential learning, or learning by doing, is an engaging, meaningful, and applicable approach to their area of interest (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Research needs to be decolonized and embrace the values of underserved areas. Students influenced by colonial frameworks are alienated from their societal challenges (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). Research should incorporate indigenous knowledge, with an emphasis on community and independence (Moxley, 2022; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). The critical study theory embraces equal access and academic freedom (Deardorff et al., 2022). Some relevant research topics that may interest students are poverty, fair trade, and the impacts

of globalization (Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). When research is of interest to the student, learning shifts from institution-centered to student-centered (Serbeh et al., 2024).

To address the issue of time constraints, one suggestion is to incorporate the research projects into the curriculum instead of making it an additional burden (Assar et al., 2022; Leonetti et al., 2023). Another suggestion is to introduce research methodology early in the curriculum, allowing students to become comfortable with it (Mahomed et al., 2021; Mehta et al., 2020; Monisha et al., 2024; Sangwa & Mutabazi, 2025). In order to achieve a higher number of publications in underserved areas, financial support and guidance will hopefully produce productivity (Monisha et al., 2024)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research questions were answered. There are diverse opinions worldwide concerning undergraduate research. Some institutions require research as a graduation requirement, while others consider it an elective opportunity. Some students view research as an obstacle, and some find it helpful. Some institutions offer research in person, while others offer it virtually. The ratio for students to faculty mentors may be 1:1, or it could be in a group setting. Global researchers must be encouraged to collaborate to achieve better outcomes. Each country views research through a different lens. Social needs and values must be incorporated into research studies to strengthen and give purpose to student research.

This study has limitations; not every country or institution was included in this review. Very little research was found concerning specific research topics. Future research should include data from countries and institutions other than those listed above. Another futuristic avenue is to continue researching virtual learning and virtual reality opportunities for research projects.

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